

STRATEGIES FOR WORKING ON THE TEXT IN DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS IN READING LITERACY LESSONS

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Abstract: This article provides general information and research results about strategies for working on texts in the development of critical thinking of elementary school students in reading literacy classes.

Key words: text, thought, critical thinking, knowledge, thinking, reading literacy,

Introduction.

It is important to develop the content of the learning process aimed at increasing students' interest in the learning process, ensuring their independence and activity, and forming their critical thinking. In this case, the need to reach the knowledge of students, to support their free observation should be satisfied first of all by teachers.

Being able to think critically is a process that can be difficult for a primary school student. In order to be able to think critically, first of all, it is necessary to understand the grammatical and phonetic aspects of the thought, that is, the student himself must understand the error and deficiency. The texts given in the "Reading Book" textbooks are a tool for the formation of speech skills in primary school students. The main purpose of reading classes in primary grades is to prepare students to understand the content of the text correctly, to be able to read consciously and expressively, to perceive the information given in the text, and to react to the reality expressed in the text. Accordingly, the primary school teacher carries out methodical training according to the purpose of the lesson, the content of the material being studied, and the level of students' existing knowledge, skills, and abilities. In preparing students to read the text of the work, first of all, attention is paid to familiarizing them with the topic, language, ideological content and artistic-aesthetic value of the text, drawing appropriate conclusions from the content of the text. Reading activity is also a special form of speech.

In the development of critical thinking, it should be taken into account that while working on the text in reading lessons, the main attention is paid to its content, but its structure should not be overlooked. In particular, the student who understands the use of past, present or future tense forms in the description of the situation, landscape, past, and psyche of the heroes of the work will not be mistaken in narrating the content of the text orally.

The scientific novelty of the article is that it is shown that there is a need for special systematic work on the formation of critical thinking in students, and the need for special training of students for it. In the formation of students' critical thinking, it is necessary to develop a set of didactic tasks, special methods, and mechanisms of pedagogical influence on students along with the development of their objective and emotional cognitive abilities.

The purpose of the research is to reveal the necessity of forming critical thinking in students and the mechanisms of pedagogical influence. The process of forming students' critical thinking was chosen as the object of the research. Systematic, comparative-logical analysis was used in the research. The empirical source of the research was the results of questionnaires. The main part. In order to increase children's interest in science and to determine their level of mastery, predict, and rationally use interpretation methods in the educational process, it is necessary to be able to clearly imagine the psychological and pedagogical features of the educational process. In order to develop critical thinking skills in children, the teacher will be able to objectively interpret this pedagogical process only if he clearly imagines the numerical indicators of individual characteristics of students in subjects.

Empirical facts have a certain relation to each other. A quantitative measurement should clearly indicate this. However, it is difficult to measure the level of mastery of the science of elementary school students who read the poem expressively and fully reflected the composition of the artistic work. Therefore, today there are the following scales according to the level of measurement:

- **nominal scale;**
- **ordinal scale;**
- **interval scale**
- **ratio or proportion scale.**

The objectivity of data analysis is of particular interest in the implementation of pedagogical-psychological coherence and continuity in the formation of critical thinking in students¹. The traditional evaluation system lacks objectivity in data analysis. For example, the same written work will be evaluated differently by different teachers, which means that the evaluation will not be objective. "Reliability" refers to the degree of reliability and accuracy of a specific trait studied.

To study the level of students' critical thinking, it is important to observe their communication processes.

The observation method is widely used to compare students' thinking and communication skills¹. The method of monitoring the level of formation of students' critical thinking in diagnoses is of great importance. The observation method helps to study and analyze the outlook, mental development, dynamics of thinking, independent expression of opinion in drawing conclusions, active point of view of students of junior school age. Active critical thinking of elementary school students also depends on the activation of their nervous systems. It appears in:

- able to overcome the difficulties they face in the process of expressing their opinion;
- show persistence in achieving the goal;
- they can perform tasks that are not so interesting for a long period of time while maintaining intensity and productivity during their educational activities;
- able to express a firm opinion by performing productive activities in various educational situations;
- striving for independence during communication and discussions;
- such as being able to show their unfamiliar, undiscovered sides in new learning situations

When creating a pedagogical system aimed at forming critical thinking skills in primary school students, it is necessary to seek answers to a number of questions:

1. In what pedagogical and psychological conditions is critical thinking formed in elementary school students?

2. What are the requirements for critical thinking of primary school students?

Creating problem situations in students' thinking activities, cultivates in them such qualities as curiosity, sharp intelligence, independence, interest in learning and striving for creativity. Results of an empirical study. In our opinion, the use of problem-based learning methods is also important in the formation of critical thinking in primary school students. Developing critical thinking skills by instilling news into their minds requires creating real pedagogical situations. This process is designed with the help of various educational concepts and theories and applied to the institutions of the educational system. It is necessary to develop the ability of objective and emotional knowledge in the formation of students' critical thinking. For this, it is necessary to develop a set of didactic tasks, special methods, mechanisms of pedagogical influence on students.

The following can be concluded from the above remarks:

1. There is a need for special systematic work on the formation of critical thinking in students.

2. Critical thinking is a set of strategies that can change the mentality of the educational audience, that is, the lesson becomes the creativity of the teacher and students. In such a process, students can master independent thinking and independent thinking through effective use of resources as a result of research and studies.

3. To create a comfortable opportunity for creative thinking among elementary school students, to accept various thoughts and ideas expressed by students with tolerance and to ensure their activity in the educational process, to establish confidence in each student's ability to think creatively, to regularly encourage their creative activities, it is necessary to develop mechanisms of pedagogical influence

Conclusion.

Based on our conclusions, we can make the following practical suggestions:

1. Although critical thinking can be defined in different ways, there is general agreement that its main component is the desire to achieve a satisfactory result, and this must be achieved through rational thinking and results-oriented work.

2. Students should gain self-confidence and understand the scope of their thoughts and ideas, actively participate in the educational process, listen carefully to different opinions, and form their own judgments. In order to teach students to think critically, the teacher should give priority to questions that provide diverse thoughts, activity, risk-taking, framing of thoughts, value of thoughts, exchange of opinions, critical thoughts.

Reimagining the text is of great importance in working on the text and develops students' critical thinking skills. The correct use of recapitulation creates favorable conditions for readers to clearly imagine the life scenes described by the writer in the work. In conclusion, in the elementary school mother tongue and reading classes, improving students' grammatical and speaking skills and increasing their creativity will ultimately serve as a factor that increases critical thinking.

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